

FIDELIS TTRAMatrix (v01.00)

Introduction & Overview (v01.00)

Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix

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Scope

The FIDELIS Transparent, Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix (TTRAM) is a simple [Matrix Template](#)¹ supported by a brief [Guide](#)².

This document provides a more detailed introduction and overview of the TTRAMatrix and how it can be deployed, populated and expanded.

The drivers behind the selection of the activities and functions (A|F), levels of retention, curation and preservation (LoRCAP) and the digital object, depositor and user characteristics supported by different repositories are covered in a separate [Design Statement](#)³. The drivers include the FIDELIS and EDEN projects, European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Task Forces, and the European Commission and EOSC perspectives on Trustworthy Digital Repositories (TDRs).

The TTRAM development has proceeded iteratively, informed by community feedback. The process is described in the milestone report [FIDELIS MS12 First Version of TTRAM](#)⁴.

Introduction: Overview

The “Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix” (TTRAM) provides a structure and reference for the FIDELIS and EDEN projects and for the emerging FIDELIS Network. This matrix is composed of:

- 30 rows representing common repository activities/functions
- A column for related transparent information
- Two columns of repository variables:
 - Levels of Retention, Curation and Preservation (LoRCAP)
 - Depositors, Users and Objects covered by different repository types.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15676331>

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15676188>

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15677075>

⁴ FIDELIS MS12 First version of TTRAM (2025). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17157958>

		Metadata, Policies, Procedures, Standards, References, Legislation etc	Variables	
Activity/ Function (A F)	Description	Transparent Information	Levels of Retention, Curation & Preservation (LoRCAP)	Repository Depositors, Users and Objects (Included & Excluded)

Transparent Information

This column supports a common understanding of the repository's practices with links and descriptions of relevant information including:

- Information Artefacts: Internal (e.g. policies, procedures) and external (e.g. guidance, legislation) documents explaining the practices.
- Repository Characteristics: Standardised repository details, including those listed in registries.

Repository Variables

These columns examine how certain characteristics shape repository functions:

- Level of Retention, Curation, and Preservation (see scale below)
- Depositors, Users and Objects included or excluded by different repository types.

These initial variables were selected as the priority for clarifying key terms relevant to the development of a coordinated, interoperable repository network.

Purpose & Implementation

The Matrix is a tool to support the FIDELIS project, the forthcoming Network and wider EOSC stakeholders in:

- **Collecting** information in a logical, reusable way
- **Understanding** the wide variety of types and practices across repositories
- **Sharing** structured information for consultation and use
- **Designing** and **implementing** a functional network of mutual support and aligned practice

Flexibility and iteration are key factors in the design. Integration of broad feedback supports each version of the matrix as repository practices are clarified and classified. Additional variables will be incorporated based on feedback and analysis of each version.

Beyond the FIDELIS and EDEN project members a wide variety of repositories, network organisations and standards developers can benefit from the TTRAM . The outputs from the Matrix will provide a model for alignment and cooperation in the Network, across EOSC and beyond.

A key focus is for the Matrix to incorporate a range of perspectives to enable mutual understanding, while avoiding limits on other ongoing activities.

The FIDELIS Matrix

The FIDELIS Matrix (TTRAM) is being used to better understand repositories⁵, and how transparency around the broad range of activities and functions (A|F) they undertake can contribute to trustworthiness.

Each A|F may be supported by business information artefacts (e.g. policies and procedures), and imply characteristics of the organisation or digital objects (expressed

⁵ While repositories are a key focus, the Matrix, and the future Network engages with a range of research data infrastructure service providers including registries. Any organisation with a catalogue that enumerates digital objects is in scope of the TTRAM.

through metadata). The A|F undertaken by repositories are influenced by a range of variables that influence the information that should be shared to foster trust, mutual support and engagement.

Variables can influence the inputs to, or the outputs from, each A|F. The overall model can be used to specify and manage additional variables that identify responsibilities and where there is a need for transparency and engagement (e.g. with data users).

The initial variables selected are:

- The levels of retention, curation and preservation (LoRCAP) being offered by a repository.
- The characteristics of Depositors, Users and Objects included or excluded by repositories. These may vary by repository type (disciplinary, generic, national, institutional etc).

Activities & Functions

The titles and descriptions of the TTRAM Activities and Functions (A|F) are included in the [Matrix Template](#)⁶ and listed in the supporting [Guide](#)⁷.

The TTRAM A|F are grouped by digital object management, organisational infrastructure, technology and security. They have been selected as a 'superset'⁸ drawn from a range of existing criteria, guidelines, requirements and standards⁹. The TTRAM is intended to support cooperation and alignment. It will complement and support engagement with those working to develop more specific and granular criteria; it is not intended to dilute or replace them.

Any information modelling decision involves some degree of compromise, but the matrix approach is designed at a human-friendly scale (not too long a list, not too deep a hierarchy), which can be mapped into more detailed approaches.

⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15676331>

⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15676188>

⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7689089>

⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7690657>

Activities & Functions of the TTRAM Matrix

For some scenarios, including assessments, a particular activity or function may not be relevant (e.g. for CoreTrustSeal¹⁰ the methods and approach to ‘access’ are not evaluated). These exceptions can simply be noted and documented while the remainder of the ‘superset’ of activities and functions remain valid across a broad range of organisations offering data and metadata services around digital objects¹¹.

Each A|F can be augmented with more detailed subsets of processes and workflows based on a particular repository or set of criteria.

¹⁰ <https://www.coretrustseal.org/why-certification/requirements/>

¹¹ It is conceptually possible to apply the Matrix to an organisation that takes no direct responsibility for data or metadata, therefore excluding all of the digital object management items.

Transparent Information

A more detailed understanding of the landscape of activities, functions, service levels and repository types helps identify what information could, should, or must be made transparent in different contexts.

- **Information Artefacts:** relevant internal (policies, procedures) and external (guidance, criteria, legislation) information.
- **Repository Characteristics:** standardised information about the repository could be made available, e.g. items from the Data Repository Attributes Working Group¹² or metadata in the FAIRsharing¹³ and re3data¹⁴ repository registries.

Note that these repository characteristics can also imply a need to share characteristics about a specific digital object based on the outcome of a repository A|F. In the case of 'Rights' this could be the specific deposit and reuse licences for an object. In the case of 'Storage & Integrity' this could be a checksum. Object-level implications are not a focus for the current version of the TTRAM, but repository/object co-dependencies need to be modelled and expressed.

One critical factor in mutual understanding and interoperability is that a desire for machine actionability drives the move from less structured prose text towards structured metadata. This also helps identify when and where human-driven intervention and assessment remains critical.

The information derived from the Matrix can support the identification of use-cases for additional machine-actionable metadata.

¹² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/data-repository-attributes-wg/outputs/?output=94428>

¹³ <https://fairsharing.org/>

¹⁴ <https://www.re3data.org/>

Variables

The Levels of Retention, Curation and Preservation

Levels of Retention, Curation and Appraisal (LoRCAP)

The selected levels of retention, curation and preservation (LoRCAP) were produced through a CoreTrustSeal community consultation, endorsed by the EOSC Long Term Data Preservation Task Force, and referenced by the EOSC Retention Task Force¹⁵.

“Z. Level Zero. Retention-only

Content distributed as deposited. Unattended deposit-storage-access. Data content and supporting metadata are stored for a given time period,

D. Deposit Compliance

Data content and supporting metadata deposited are checked for compliance with defined criteria

C. Initial Curation

The digital objects are curated by the repository to meet defined criteria

A. Active preservation

Long-term responsibility for ensuring that the data and metadata can be understood and rendered as required by the designated community for reuse”

¹⁵ CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board. (2024). Curation & Preservation Levels: CoreTrustSeal Position Paper. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11476980>

Repository Depositors, Users and Objects

Commonly referred to repository types include:

- Institutional
- Regional, National, International
- Generalist
- Disciplinary/Domain/Specialist

These labels are not, alone, sufficient to understand a repository. The variable focuses on characteristics that cause objects, depositors or users to be included or excluded from the repository collection and/or services:

- Depositors accepted/rejected e.g. based on institutional affiliation.
- Users accepted/rejected e.g. based on geographic location.
- Digital objects types and content accepted/rejected for deposit, curation, preservation and access e.g. based on a discipline.

Collecting information and clarifying these points supports a clearer typology of repositories, identifies where a repository requires particular skills and expertise, and indicates areas where more specific and machine-actionable metadata about repositories would be desirable.

Building on the Initial Variables

The initial variables have been selected as primary targets to provide more granular and specific information than is provided by current repository types and varied definitions of 'preservation'.

Different levels of retention, deposit compliance, curation and preservation may imply a need for activities around technical monitoring (of formats and software) and for monitoring changing community needs. This monitoring can inform decisions to take semantic or logical preservation actions (e.g. updates to ontologies, metadata and documentation, or file format conversions). Restrictions on the scope of depositors, collections and users in different repository types will influence whether a researcher should or could select them for their research outputs.

Understanding these key variables, and how they interact, will provide the foundation for a common vision and for the exploration of additional relevant variables.

Applicability Beyond TDRs

The majority of the A|F described in the Matrix apply beyond any narrow 'repository' definition¹⁶. Transparent and consistent descriptions of organisational *mission and scope* are a dependency for effective use of the Matrix. The repositories depend on wider partnerships of metadata and data services from storage providers, to high performance computing, to multiple registries; all these play a critical role in research data infrastructure.

One example is the 'technical repository service providers' developing a 'community-based catalogue of requirements'¹⁷ through an RDA working group¹⁸. This technical service provision perspective can be integrated into the TTRAM while allowing this more granular and specific work to progress.

Trust & Trustworthiness in Context

Trust is not a binary and static outcome of a single, one-size-fits-all assessment.

Defining trustworthiness in (meaningful) contexts depends on understanding objects, actors, roles, and expected levels of service. These in turn make it clear that an assessment of trustworthiness needs to be based on reliable, transparent information.

Modelling and defining different trust contexts, including authority over criteria, assessment and outcomes, will be an important part of future TTRAM work.

¹⁶Hervé L'Hours, & Darren Bell. (2023). Review of CoreTrustSeal Applicability to non-Preservation (Trustworthy) Data Services (v02.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7646134>

¹⁷ https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1PCPbuzZ7BQOt2q_mkmB9IM6H1peCak3F9_JbDoXwg3c/

¹⁸ Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group (TRSPs WG) <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/community-based-catalogue-requirements-trustworthy-technical-repository-service-providers/activity/>

Dependencies & Interdependencies

The TTRAM takes account of a range of influences including the past and current EOSC Task Forces and the EC, Horizon Europe Annotated Model Grant Agreement which provides a perspective on essential criteria for 'trust'. These are outlined briefly below and covered in more detail by the associated Design Statement¹⁹.

The activities, functions, levels of curation and preservation, and future variables, will all support the work on Network Governance and Value Add (FIDELIS Pillar 2) that is considering the potential interests, priorities and concerns of future Network members and stakeholders.

For the FIDELIS Training and Support (Pillar 4) and Strategic Alliance, Cascading Grants, Communication and Dissemination (Pillar 5), and the EDEN Expert and Community Engagement (WP4), the language of the activities and functions and future work on the variables can support alignment.

A key reason to remain flexible and to iterate is to allow the EDEN project to make progress on the Data and Process Framework for Long-Term Digital Preservation (WP1) and Discipline-specific Requirements, Validation and Future Use (WP3). Outputs on Long-term Access and Preservation Services & Tools (WP2) will align with other EDEN work, allowing the FIDELIS matrix to expand its variables to a range of service catalogues and supporting technologies.

EDEN outputs will provide essential, robust and granular specifications of key concepts, including addressing reappraisal and quality criteria. These can then be integrated into the Matrix where relevant, specifically around active long term preservation repositories and disciplinary repositories and technical services.

In addition to the above, the Matrix will support ongoing alignment with existing criteria and metadata. This will require planning for how outputs (e.g. crosswalks) should be presented, versioned and maintained for maximum usability to a broader audience.

¹⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15677075>

TTRAM Deployment, Population, Iteration

The FIDELIS Matrix supports a more granular understanding of repository types and how transparency of information around their A|F, influenced by different variables, can contribute to trustworthiness.

Rather than creating another set of criteria, the approach is inclusive and aligned with a range of existing expert perspectives to support classification, communication and assistance. This is important in an environment where critical items already have existing, established and well-adopted criteria in place, including IT service management²⁰ and information security²¹.

The local relevance of A|F will depend on the organisational mission and scope of services. For example, a *retention-only* repository may define 'deposit & appraisal', 'curation quality', 'preservation' and 'reuse' as 'not applicable'. 'Trustworthy' status is not the result of a single immutable assessment, but an ongoing goal that depends on understanding the needs of the parties involved and the level of responsibility they assume for digital objects.

The matrix supports flexible alignment within the projects, with key stakeholders and Network members, and with the authors of referenced criteria. This enables an iterative approach to cooperating with repositories and criteria authors to reach a shared perspective on mutual support and trust within a robust network.

The Matrix is not limited to the variables presented above. Similar approaches can be used for the FAIR²² and CARE²³ and TRUST²⁴ Principles, the use of a specific technical

²⁰ See e.g. the FitSM standard: <https://www.fitsm.eu/>

²¹ ISO/IEC 27001:2022 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection — Information security management systems — Requirements: <https://www.iso.org/standard/27001>

²² Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

²³ Carroll, S.R., Garba, I., Figueroa-Rodríguez, O.L., Holbrook, J., Lovett, R., Materechera, S., Parsons, M., Raseroka, K., Rodriguez-Lonebear, D., Rowe, R., Sara, R., Walker, J.D., Anderson, J. and Hudson, M. (2020) 'The CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance', *Data Science Journal*, 19(1), p. 43. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-043>

²⁴ Lin, D., Crabtree, J., Dillo, I. et al. The TRUST Principles for digital repositories. *Sci Data* 7, 144 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7>

solution (e.g. Dataverse²⁵), the presence of a particular digital object characteristic (e.g. sensitivity of special category data) or factors around the emergence of EOSC service Nodes²⁶ and Data Spaces²⁷.

As the Matrix is populated and expanded it will become useful for a range of potential actors, from those seeking clear guidance (“if you’re doing X then share Y”) to those aligning evidence and practice from multiple criteria to specify machine-actionable metadata. In this way it can be maintained as a common reference point for future Network members, activities, communication, training and expert groups.

A more granular understanding of repository types and services will support future FIDELIS Network activities that seek to meet community needs and provide a community voice. Ongoing alignment of the Matrix with emerging expectations of repositories will enable cooperation, progress and compliance, including interoperability with the emerging European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) infrastructure.

Within the lifetime of the project(s), the Matrix will support categorisation of actors and activities. Beyond that, it will support an engaged network seeking to align efforts, to clarify existing challenges and address new ones.

²⁵ <https://dataverse.org/>

²⁶ <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/>

²⁷ <https://eosc.eu/events/data-spaces-symposium-2/>

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²⁸ <https://www.data-archive.ac.uk/>

²⁹ <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/>

³⁰ <https://www.essex.ac.uk/about/faculty-of-social-sciences>

³¹ <https://www.fsd.tuni.fi/en/>

³² <https://www.tuni.fi/en>

³³ <https://www.gesis.org>

³⁴ <https://www.sib.swiss/>

³⁵ <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/>

³⁶ <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/who-we-are/hub>

³⁷ <https://en.uit.no/>

³⁸ <https://csc.fi/en/>

Abbreviations and Acronyms

A F	Activity or Function drawn from the reference list of Activities and Functions.
CARE	Principles for Indigenous Data Governance: Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, Ethics
CoreTrustSeal	CoreTrustSeal is an international, community based, non-profit organization promoting sustainable and trustworthy data infrastructures.
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud aims to provide researchers and innovators in Europe with an open and trusted multi-disciplinary environment to publish, find and reuse data, tools and services.
FAIR	Principles designed to make research data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable.
FitSM	FitSM is a free and lightweight standards family aimed at facilitating service management in IT service provision, including federated scenarios.
ISO27001	International standard for information security management
LoRCAP	Levels of retention, curation and preservation
RDA	Research Data Alliance
TDR	Trustworthy Digital Repository
TRUST	Principles that define the characteristics of trustworthy digital repositories: Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability and Technology.
TTRAM	Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix